

D2.2 Prototype Text Mining Solution

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Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Executive Summary

This report describes the progress made on the Text Mining (TM) solution tool for the Polirural project. It complements the Deliverable 2.2 which is the Demo of the Prototype for the PoliRural's Text Mining (TM) solution. The link to the Semantic Explorer prototype is: <http://semex.io/>.

The main components developed are the Topic Manager, the Profiler, the Curated Reading Lists and the Sentiment Analysis and various data visualizations. These modules will support Polirural's researchers, data Analysts and Software Developers in Foresight Activities, System Dynamic Modelling and policy evaluation.

Further efforts from WP2 will be needed in order to complete the product by May 2020. The actual prototype is correctly working, but fine-tuning, also based on Polirural partners' inputs, will be necessary.

1. Introduction

This report describes the progress made on the Text Mining (TM) solution tool for the Polirural project, so-called Semantic Explorer. It complements Deliverable 2.2 which is the Demo of the Prototype for the Polirural's Text Mining Solution. The link to the prototype is: <http://semex.io/>. Access to the library for reviewing purposes can be requested to denis.kolokol@kajoservices.com.

As introduced in the Text Mining Technical Specifications (Deliverable 2.1) the creation of the TM solution in the context of this project will support Polirural experts' analysis about local challenges and needs. It will also contribute to provide policy makers with more accurate and timely information at various stages of the decision-making process. In particular, Polirural Pilots' workshops will extensively use regional Foresight exercises in order to understand change, how it happens and what causes it. The Semantic Explorer has been therefore designed taking into consideration its use within a Regional Foresight exercise and as a support tool also for System Dynamics (SDM). The ambition is to reach the objective of creating a tool that will also support policymakers by extracting relevant information available on Internet as selected by Pilots and partners through the Regional Library. The system is intended to collect data from Social Media, in particular opinions, and their relationship to various aspects of policies. This will allow for comparing the analysis with quantitative data, obtained through surveys, and to provide "one version of the truth" through interactive visuals.

2. Defining the use-cases and the end-users

The TM solutions have been specifically designed to provide inputs to Polirural experts on Foresight activities, System Dynamics Modelling and policy evaluation. The tool will be based on Machine Learning and NLP and will have, as first end-users, researchers, data analysts and Software Developers. Partners and Pilots from Polirural consortium will be able to compare, for example, the results coming from surveys with the outputs of the Semantic Explorer.

2.1 Integrating Text Mining in a Foresight Activity

"Foresight methodologies seek to gather data and make sense of it so that people can think in different and new ways about the future. That data might be collected from humans or from the analysis of documents and artefacts, or both" (Conway, 2014). TM is able to analyse and summarize the vast amount of information available on the Internet and can thus provide the initial input for Foresight activities.

The prototype created by KAJO reflects intense consultation between WP2, WP4, WP5 and Pilots and will assist the Foresight activities with the following solutions:

2.1.1 Topic Manager for Horizon Scanning

Horizon scanning serves a purpose of identifying relevant trends that may impact the region. The result is a list of topics crucial in the analysis of a specific pilot. This process could for instance highlight trends in relation to time and to a specific topic from which experts could extrapolate something comparable to Mega and Micro Trends and other high-level drivers of change.

The components of **Topic Manager** address this task and in the prototype is realized for English language.

Navigating topics can be accessed at the link: <http://semex.io/>. Text can be analysed by extracting relevant topics based on keywords' extraction (TextRank algorithm). It can also generate topic similarity clusters – given a root topic a tree of subtopics is extracted from the model and filtered by actual topics contained in text. Various interactive visualisations of subtopic graphs, as the ones that are displayed here below, provide for easy exploration of the topic similarity space and discovering of hidden relations.

Figure 1 Navigating topics - Tree View.

Figure 2 Navigating topics - Radial Tree View

Similarity cluster is a special kind of representation of topics, whose example is given on Figure 3. Clicking the button "Explore in Library" affects in changing the view to Topic Browser, in which the topics of the first level and its subtopics are connected to the sources from the Regional Library.

Figure 3 Topics connected to Regional Library

2.1.2 Profiler for Issues and Needs analysis

Issues and needs analysis should capture well-known or recognised needs that are already mentioned in policy documents, as well as anticipate future local needs based on the dynamics of regional development. This process could be used for Deep-Dives to localize the impact of relevant trends at regional level. The Profiler sub-component of the Semantic Explorer is designed to solve this task.

NUI Galway Rural Studies **ORG** are delighted to be part of the new **four year DATE** **European NORP** # **H2020 PERSON** RURALIZATION project.

Led by Dr. **Maura Farrell PERSON** the project will develop knowledge to support policy making for rural regeneration focused on access to land, youth visions for rural futures, newcomers to rural areas and new entrants to farming. Great team involved in the project from **the Rural Studies Cluster - ORG** Dr. **Marie Mahon PERSON** , Dr. **Therese Conway PERSON** , Dr. **John McDonagh PERSON** , Dr. **Shane Conway PERSON** and Dr. **Aisling Murtagh PERSON** as Post-Doctoral Researcher.

The project started on **May 1st DATE** and the kick-off meeting was held in **Barcelona GPE** **last week DATE** . Check out the project fact sheet on **Cordis ORG** : bit.ly/2HxN29J

#FARMVIABILITY The **NRN ORG** has just published a new case study on **Social Farming ORG** in **Ireland GPE** .

Social farming allows participants to engage in everyday activities on ordinary working farms, helping to increase their social skills, self-esteem and confidence while also helping to improve their health and wellbeing by being out in the natural environment. Participants come from a range of backgrounds including people experiencing mental health issues, people with disabilities, and refugees, among others.

Tommy Earley Mountallen Eco PERSON **Tours GPE** , a farmer who hosts social farming placements on his farm in **Drumshanbo GPE** , Co. Leitrim and gives his experience of social farming in this case study, states that "You know activities can be wide ranging you could be looking at leaves on trees, looking at flowers, or picking spuds or splitting sticks but it doesn't matter what you're doing, it's that the person or whoever is doing it is happy out at what they are doing".

To learn more about **Social Farming ORG** in **Ireland GPE** and **Tommys PERSON** experience of being involved in **Social Farming ORG** please read the full case study here <https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/farm-viability-case-studies/national-rural-network-social-farming-case-study/>

Social Farming GPE Ireland West Limerick Resources - WLR Leitrim Development Company Waterford Leader Partnership CLG South West Mayo Development Company CLG

Funding is available under the CLAR Programme, Town and Village Renewal Scheme, **Rural Recreation Programme ORG** and the **LEADER ORG** programme to enhance and develop rural towns and villages socially, culturally, and economically.

Full details and forms are available at <https://www.westmeathcoco.ie/en/ourservices/communitydevelopment/ruralsupports/>

Please contact our Community Development Section on **044 933 2258 CARDINAL** with queries.

Submit applications by **Friday 27 March 2020 DATE** . Westmeath Community Development

Figure 4 Representation of Profiler

Automatic Named Entity Recognition (NER) is performed automatically for all texts that can be extracted from sources in the Regional Library. The types of entities are given in the following table¹:

TYPE	DESCRIPTION
PERSON	People, including fictional.
NORP	Nationalities or religious or political groups.
FAC	Buildings, airports, highways, bridges, etc.
ORG	Companies, agencies, institutions, etc.
GPE	Countries, cities, states.

¹ Taken from the documentation of spaCy: <https://spacy.io/api/annotation#named-entities>

LOC	Non-GPE locations, mountain ranges, bodies of water.
PRODUCT	Objects, vehicles, foods, etc. (Not services.)
EVENT	Named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events, etc.
WORK_OF_ART	Titles of books, songs, etc.
LAW	Named documents made into laws.
LANGUAGE	Any named language.
DATE	Absolute or relative dates or periods.
TIME	Times smaller than a day.
PERCENT	Percentage, including "%".
MONEY	Monetary values, including unit.
QUANTITY	Measurements, as of weight or distance.
ORDINAL	"first", "second", etc.
CARDINAL	Numerals that do not fall under another type.

Table 1 Named Entities labels and types

Automatic recognition of Entities is a useful tool both for Foresight activities and for System Dynamics modelling.

2.1.3 Curated Reading Lists

A productive and effective Foresight exercise requires a lot of preparation based on research and a lot of reading. This includes having access to a lot of sources, being subscribed to many groups in social media and following discussion boards in order to be able to spot hot topics and trends. A submodule for creation and updating Curated Reading Lists helps to stay up to date by extracting relevant and timely information from the constantly updated sources. Curated reading lists will be functional as soon as Pilots and Partners will start to populate the library with specific links to literature and databases and the first Issues and Needs analysis will be performed.

2.2 Using Text Mining inputs to create System Dynamics Models

2.2.1 Pilot profiling (for SDM)

Pilot profiling (for SDM) aims at understanding the normal course of action and identifying trends or behaviours over time when modelling with local agents or communities. The outputs from the **Profiler** sub-component of Semantic Explorer are expected to help in this process by creating pilot profiles. In particular, the Profiler will help SDM in characterizing the following issues:

- Region
- Issues to be addressed
- Dynamics

The results are dynamics in the form of pieces of text that can be easily translated into models. The dynamics are linked to the issues previously identified, and more than one dynamic may be linked to every issue.

2.3 Sentiment analysis: measuring people's perception about policies on social media

Sentiment analysis is performed automatically for each new source added to the library. In the prototype, sentiment analysis is executable for English-based resources only.

MTK is an interest organization representing farmers, forest owners and rural entrepreneurs in Finland. In 2017 MTK celebrated its 100 years of anniversary together with 100 years anniversary of Finland's independence. [0.7717](#)

MTK has over 324 000 members in local agricultural producers' organisations and regional forest management associations. All of the occupations and businesses of our members are based on renewable natural resources and their utilisation in a sustainable and economical way. [0.3612](#)

Regional activities and lobbying are carried out by 14 provincial MTK unions and 62 forest management associations. [-0.0772](#)

According to a recent study carried out by University of Helsinki MTK is considered to be in top three of the most influential interest groups in Finland. [0.8059](#)

MTK's sister organisation, SLC, has approximately 13,000 members and operates in the Swedish-speaking areas of Finland.

Community of Security, Equality, and Sustainable Development MTK. [0.34](#)

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 Tietoa evästeistä

Figure 5 Sentiment Analysis

Figure 5 shows the sentiment analysis performed on a given text displaying scores highlighted in blue or red. The **sentiment analysis** tool is developed in order to quantify the overall feeling of a sentence and categorize it into a scale from **-1** (very negative) to 0 (neutral) to **+1** (very positive).

This system can therefore quantify the sentiments of public opinions expressed on social media (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) regarding a certain topic or specific policy. The results can be plotted and represented with various visualizations that will be developed at the front-end. It will then be possible to display the results on a map visualizing how the sentiments about certain policies differs in the various regions considered. The possibility of integrating such an option in the Innovation Hub has already been discussed and should be further explored. Other possibilities include comparative diagrams such as histograms, bar graphs etc. Furthermore, with several iterations and by comparing the results with more traditional approach to research such as survey, it may be even possible to extrapolate the reasons that determined positivity or negativity in social media discussions.

2.4 Pipelines: merging the solutions, enhancing the results of Text Mining

Beside the case-studies listed in the sections above, KAJO, together with other partners, evaluated the possibility of providing a series of more structured TM functions, a sort of

collection of pre-cooked recipes, blending together some of the solutions for enhancing the overall functionality of the product. These processes are defined as pipelines and briefly discussed in this sub-chapter.

The nature of Foresight Exercise, System Dynamics Modeling and Policy Evaluation is dynamic and iterative. Each process is a chain of *actions*. The result of each action (or several actions) can serve as an input for successive steps. The whole chain can be repeated iteratively using the results of the previous cycle as the input for the next one.

The current section discusses pipelines that help define actions vs. results for the creation of a user interface. As each pipeline is represented as a single workspace, every parameter change should affect the result of all successive stages immediately (the AJAX interaction).

The user-system interaction is based on the following concepts:

- *Actions*
- *Pipeline*
- *Workspace*

By *action* we understand the use of a module of Semantic Explorer, which takes user input, performs a single action on the data and returns output. The types of actions:

- a call to a particular method of TextProcessor or TextAnalyzer (e.g. `.topics()`, `.sentiment()`, etc.)
- data filtering (for example, filtering SM posts by time frame and topics)
- aggregation of values obtained in the course of a previous action (e.g. averaging sentiments or displaying gathered data on a timeline).

The pipeline is an internal representation of the process. Each pipeline consists of a defined number of actions. A user interface for each action is a *workspace*.

Workspace is a particular arrangement of visual elements on a web-page, that are organized in a sensible way and together provide a way to define the whole Pipeline in a single view.

The relations between those three concepts can be represented by the following diagram:

Figure 6 Relation between actions, pipeline and workspace

Pipelines will be an integral part of the final product. A detailed description will be included in Deliverable 2.3.

3. Regional Library

3.1 Inputs

For the creation of the Regional Library KAJO created a questionnaire and circulated it to all Pilots' leaders. The twelve pilots sent their data, which have been converted to database records (see the next chapter).

Each Pilot filled the questionnaire giving their inputs on the following points:

- Links to policy documents from all levels (EU, national, regional, local)
- Links to Pilots' related websites
- List of social media used and accounts/groups, if available
- Names of regional landscapes
- Key search words
- Relevant words according to stakeholders

Table 2 summarizes the inputs received by Pilots for each point.

Regional Landscapes	Key search words	Topics	Needs	Links	Related Websites	Social Media	Total
97	261	241	145	311	290	104	1449

Table 2 Library content after first collection

These figures shall increase following further inputs from Pilots and from WP4 D4.3 Regional Library For Policy Evaluation that will provide a second batch of data.

3.2 Storage

The Regional Library is present in two different forms:

- Plain data storage (links and texts) - MongoDB² (currently single node).
- Indexed data for search and analysis - distributed Index in the Elasticsearch³ cluster.

3.3 Access to data

3.3.1 Regional Library

Partners can access the Regional Library for adding new sources and/or editing those that were uploaded from the questionnaire mentioned in Deliverable 2.1 "Inputs". It is available for registered users only in the form of the web admin panel. In the current stage of the project the access is offered only to project's partners. These received extensive training by WP2 leader Denis Kolokol on the use of the Library through a dedicated webinar in December 2019 and a "hands-on" training in January 2020.

Direct link to access Regional Library Management page: <http://semex.io/app/sources/>. The link opens a list view of Regional Library, in which sources can be filtered by language, source type, the content type of the source in the internet (pdf, html, etc.) and by the owner (partner). In the List view it is possible to add a new source, to edit existing or to delete selected resources⁴.

² <https://www.mongodb.com/>

³ <https://www.elastic.co/>

⁴ End-user can only delete a source if he/she is an owner of that source

Each library source has its own page where end-users can update URL or language. In this page there are also results of semantic analysis: extracted topics, text with highlighted named entities, the result of semantic analysis (by paragraph) and links to external resources automatically extracted from text. The following figure is a print-screen of the Library source management application where it is possible to distinguish the list of documents and the possible filters that the end-user can apply.

3.3.2 Integration with Crawlers

The Prototype of the Text Mining solution includes its own crawlers, but in a very limited version: it is capable of handling only well-written SGML resources (such as HTML or XML) and PDF files. Moreover, it can only obtain text from the provided page, not "looking" inside the structure of the web-site (so, links to other parts of the web-site are omitted). At the same time the prototype is fully equipped with integration tools and will use Crawlers written by another partner of the project (NUVIT) as soon as they are ready for integration.

The screenshot displays the 'Library source management' application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the text 'WELCOME, KAJO_ADMIN. VIEW SITE / CHANGE PASSWORD / LOG OUT' and a breadcrumb trail 'Home > Sources > Library'. Below the navigation bar, the main heading is 'Select Library Source to change'. To the right of this heading is a button labeled 'ADD LIBRARY SOURCE +'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a search bar with a magnifying glass icon and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar is an 'Action:' dropdown menu with a 'Go' button and the text '0 of 100 selected'. The main part of the left column is a table listing library sources. The table has two columns: 'ID' and 'URL'. Each row starts with a checkbox. The URLs listed are: <https://www.facebook.com/lokalnyrolnikpl/>, <https://twitter.com/nauksenuovads>, <https://twitter.com/Jaunpiebalga>, https://twitter.com/Lubanas_novads, https://twitter.com/Cesvaine_novads, <https://twitter.com/beverinasnovads>, <https://twitter.com/ergluinfo>, https://twitter.com/Mazsalaca_LV, and <https://twitter.com/InstaNovads>. The right column is a 'FILTER' sidebar. It has three sections: 'By language', 'By source type', and 'By content-type'. Under 'By language', there are options for 'All', 'Čeština (Czech)', 'Ελληνικά (Greek)', 'English (English)', 'Español (Spanish)', 'Suomi (Finnish)', 'עברית (Hebrew)', 'Italiano (Italian)', 'Latviešu (Latvian)', 'Македонски (Macedonian)', 'Vlaams (Flemish)', 'Polski (Polish)', and 'Slovenčina (Slovak)'. Under 'By source type', there are options for 'All', 'General', 'Social Media', 'Scientific', 'Report', and 'Other'. Under 'By content-type', there is an option for 'All'.

Figure 7 Library source management - list view

3.3.3 Regions (Pilots)

The link to manage regions: <http://semex.io/app/regions/region/>.

3.3.4 Landscapes

Each region includes one or more landscapes, that can be managed here:

<http://semex.io/app/regions/landscape/>.

4. Additional features

4.1 External Links extraction

External links are URLs found in the text of each source in the library. They are being extracted automatically upon adding a source to the library and displayed in the detailed view.

5 Access to data and services via API

Warning: for all endpoints described below a username and API-key is necessary.

5.1 Library management

The main API endpoint for extraction list of resources from Library:

http://semex.io/api/v1/library/?format=json&username=XXX&api_key=YYY

Detailed view of a particular source:

http://semex.io/api/v1/library/source_id?format=json&username=XXX&api_key=YYY

Updating resource:

```
curl --location --request POST
'http://semex.io/api/v1/library/source_id/?username=XXX' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
  "url": "<url data>"
}'
```

Creating new resource:

```
curl --location --request POST
http://semex.io/api/v1/library/?username=XXX \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
  "url": "https://www.hameenliitto.fi/en",
  "name": "Haame",
  "description": "Websites for Regional Council",
  "lang": "en"
}'
```

5.2 Semantic features

5.2.1 Text Analysis

```
curl --location --request POST
http://semex.io/api/v1/analyze/?username=XXX \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
  "text": "Irish food is produced by thousands of farmers,
fishermen and agri-food companies around the country, and this
locally produced food is exported to over 180 countries around the
world, with agri-food exports totalling over €13.6 billion in 2017.
This supply chain, stretching from rural and coastal areas all
across Ireland to distant markets in Asia and Africa underlines the
sector's pivotal role as a driver of the Irish economy. Food safety
and environmental sustainability are both crucial to maintaining our
existing markets and developing new market opportunities. Irish food
is produced to the highest international standards of quality and
food safety. Our food safety and traceability systems continue to be
recognised as among the very best in the world.",
  "pipeline": ["polarity", "ner"],
  "lang": "en"
}'
```

NB: the use of parameter 'pipeline' will be explained in the User Manual of the system in its final stage, because new functionalities are supposed to be added if requested by the partners of the project.

5.2.2 External URL and/or Library Source Analysis

This involves Crawling prior to analysis. Calling this endpoint also automatically saved the link in the Library. If the source is already in the Library, its ID can be given Instead of the URL.

```
curl --location --request POST
'http://semex.io/api/v1/analyze/?username=XXX' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--data-raw '{
  "url":
"https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agricultural_productivity",
  "pipeline": ["sentiment", "topics"],
  "lang": "en"
}'
```

6 Special considerations

6.1 Multiple Languages vs. Available Libraries

There are two main factors that defined the design of the future TM solution and the selection of the tools used in its development:

- Multilingual character of the project
- Popularity of a package or a library (which means a good community and a support)

Out of all the open-source solutions two main libraries for Text Mining tasks were selected: spaCy⁵ and Gensim⁶. They are being used for different purposes: Gensim is the main library for Topic Management, while spaCy is being adopted in Profiler (to complete such tasks as Named Entity Recognition [NER]) as well as general tasks of keywords extraction and Sentiment Analysis.

SpaCy is an NLP library distributed with the pre-trained language-dependent models. In the current deliverable of the PoliRural project the following languages are covered:

- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- Flemish
- Greek

It also allows for training custom models, which in the next stage will be used for:

- fine tuning of the models in existing languages
- training models for the languages not yet covered.

In its turn Gensim is used for training word2vec models and does not have any pre-trained models. It is used for Topic Management and in the first stage of the project (Working Prototype) is ready in English language. We will need help from Partners for training models in the rest of the languages.

7 Conclusions

This report complements the prototype of the semantic explorer (<http://semex.io/>) that has been developed within WP2, following intense consultation with WP4, WP5 and Pilots. During the development process it became obvious that in Polirural an important part of research will be carried out through Foresight activities and System Dynamics Modelling. For this reason, the tools have been developed specifically for bringing relevant inputs to FS and SDM. Moreover, the sentiment analysis component is capable of extracting important insights from social media that can complement or be compared with results from more traditional research such as policy evaluation and surveys. Researchers, data Analysts and Software Developers from Pilots will be provided with various TM tools that will support their research by extracting structured data from unstructured text for further analysis. The development of specific pipelines combining the various components in several iterations will dig even deeper in the information available on the Internet.

It can be argued that a good amount of the back-end work has been completed. At this stage of the prototype all the components that were thought in Deliverable 2.1 are working. These include the Topic Manager, the Profiler, the Pilot Profiler, the Curated Reading List Manager, the Sentiment Analysis. The various visualizations created so far display the results in a meaningful and clear way. Finally, infrastructure has been deployed and the system is stable and functional.

⁵ <https://spacy.io/>

⁶ <https://pypi.org/project/gensim/>

However, impressive efforts will be necessary in order to develop the final product by May 2020. Most of the resources will be engaged in developing a user interface able to present a powerful tool in a straightforward display. This means working on the interface, but it also entails a great deal of work in the back-end in order to match the interface requirements and objectives. Particular attention will be dedicated in the creation of the various pipelines or processes that blend the components together. Moreover, the ambitious objective of a semantic explorer working for twelve languages will imply a lot of resources and the results are not predictable. It will be necessary to make a priority list and determine which languages are more important for Polirural. For instance, in some countries such as Israel, a lot of material is available and consulted in English, reducing the necessity of analysing text in the local language. Another solution could be the automatic translation of texts, which however involves some additional costs and can alter the meaning or the sentiment of text. Finally, further involvement from Pilots and from WP4 will be necessary in order to enlarge the Regional Library. Partners have received enough training (during the technical training in Madrid in January 2020) for entering new and more relevant entries or sources. It will be essential that the crawlers provided by NUVIT are stable and work flawlessly.

The TM system will be continuously tested also with the involvement of Pilots and technical partners. We are planning a trial involving Text Mining, System Dynamics and Foresight activities in the Flemish Pilot managed by VITO. The results shall be described in a journal paper. This will be a good opportunity to put into practice the system and the options foreseen. Moreover, the final product that will be ready by May 2020 will still necessitate further testing and fine-tuning. Feedbacks from Pilots and technical partners will be of great importance and for this reason we will enhance communication directly with Pilots and partners as well as with the support of Polirural's Coordinators.

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